

Citation for the Presentation of the 2019
ICPE Medal to

Professor Pratibha Jolly
India

at 3rd World Conference on Physics Education
Hanoi, Vietnam
December 2021

Professor Pratibha Jolly is awarded the ICPE Medal for 2019 in recognition of her sustained contributions to physics education and outreach.

Dr. Jolly gained a Ph.D. in Theoretical Chemical Physics in 1980 from University of Delhi. She began her academic career in 1980 at her *alma mater* Miranda House, a constituent college for women at the University of Delhi. Her interests soon veered towards innovation and research in physics education at the tertiary level. In 1988, she moved to the University Department of Physics and Astrophysics as Research Scientist, setting up a laboratory for learning through investigative projects and integrating computers in physics education. This attracted students from across the university and beyond. In April 2005, she was nudged to move back to Miranda House to lead the college as principal, a post she held for fourteen years till February 2019. Under her dynamic leadership, Miranda House received All India Rank One under the National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF), a feat sustained for five successive years from 2017 to 2021.

Dr. Jolly was the Chairperson of ICPE for six years from October 2005 to 2011, having served as member first from 2002 to 2005. During this period, she set a new agenda for the Commission urging greater engagement with outstanding problems. The high point of her tenure was launch of *Physware* series of active learning *Educate the Educator* workshops designed to strengthen teaching of physics, especially in the developing world, with support from the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP). She co-designed and co-directed along with a distinguished international team, pilot *Physware* Workshops in 2009 (at ICTP) and 2012 (at Delhi). These efforts created a global network of regional leaders who began promoting active learning workshops and physics education research programmes in their own countries. Strengthening of

cooperation with other apex physics education organizations led to launch of the quadrennial World Conference on Physics Education (WCPE) series in 2012.

Dr. Jolly has several pioneering research projects to her credit that have led to pedagogical innovation and development of educational resource materials. Her multifaceted work led to establishment of the *D S Kothari Centre for Research and Innovation in Science Education* at Miranda House. The centre has catalysed creation of technology enhanced active teaching-learning environments, promoted project-based learning, interdisciplinary and collaborative undergraduate research. It has also spearheaded innovative faculty development programmes, capacity building of women in science and leadership roles and science outreach programmes at all levels. The activities have made an impact at national and international level.

Dr. Jolly is a role model and a thought leader who is passionate about engendering change. She is currently leading in her country the pilot of an innovative policy intervention programme titled GATI (Gender Advancement for Transforming Institutions) which entails developing a self-assessment framework for promoting gender equity in STEM disciplines.

For her wide-ranging contributions, ICPE is happy to present the 2019 Medal to Professor Pratibha Jolly jointly with Professor Alex Mazzolini (Australia).

Professor Roberto Nardi and Professor Pratibha Jolly during the 3rd WCPE – ICPE Virtual Medal Ceremony.

Roberto Nardi
ICPE Chair